

Abstract

Practical Foundations for Chikung (Qigong) Practice.

Jorge Magalhães Rodrigues^{1*}

¹ IPTC - Research Department in Complementary Therapies, Portuguese Institute of *Taiji* and *Qigong*, Porto, Portugal.

* Correspondence: dep.Investig-IPTC@outlook.pt

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Chikung (*Qigong*) is a traditional Chinese discipline that integrates movement, breath, and mind regulation to cultivate and balance vital energy (*Qi*). This communication explores the essential practical foundations that underpin effective *Qigong* practice, categorising the exercises into core pillars: intention, stretching, posture, for the cultivation of *Qi*.

The technical application of these foundations involves:

- **Intention (Yi):** The use of energy visualisation to mobilise *Qi* within the body according to specific therapeutic goals. This can be achieved through static postures, such as the *Zhan Zhuang* system, or through physical movement.
- **Stretching of Channels:** Practical exercises focused on the objective stretching of energy channels (*Jing Mai* or *Jing Luo Gong*), which can be performed with or without specific energetic visualisation.
- **Posture and Alignment:** The establishment of a "smooth" posture that facilitates a connection between the Earth (*Yin* energy) and the Heaven (*Yang* energy).

Crucially, these practical elements are not merely physical; research indicates that posture regulation has a direct impact on both physiological and affective states. Scientific evidence demonstrates that specific postures can influence cardiovascular control, plasma catecholamines, and mood states during rest and mental stress. By understanding these interactions between the

physical and the mental, practitioners can better utilise *Qigong* as a tool for physiological regulation and psychological well-being.

Keywords: *Qigong*; Qi Cultivation; Posture Regulation; Intention; Mind-Body Interaction.

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